
Project Title	SCAlable LAttice Boltzmann Leaps to Exascale
Project Acronym	SCALABLE
Grant Agreement No.	956000
Start Date of Project	01.01.2021
Duration of Project	36 Months
Project Website	www.scalable-hpc.eu

D4.3

D4.3 : The Final Report on the Optimizations

Work Package	WP 4: Performance Modelling and Optimisation
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Reviewed By	
Due Date	31.12.2023
Date	
Version	1.0

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
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The Scalable project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 956000.

Deliverable Information

Deliverable	D4.3
Deliverable Type	Report
Deliverable Title	D4.3 : The Final Report on the Optimizations
Keywords	
Dissemination Level	
Work Package	WP 4: Performance Modelling and Optimisation
Lead Partner	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
Lead Author	Jayesh Badwaik (FZJ)
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Planned Date	
Version	1.0
Final Version Date	

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December 22, 2023

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Part 1

Walberla

Node-Level Optimizations

1.1 HRR Kernel

Over the past two decades, the LBM has grown to become a reliable alternative to classical CFD that is based on solving the discretized Navier-Stokes equations. Its advantages are a simple basic algorithmic structure and very low computational cost per degree of freedom.

The basic idea of the LBM is to solve the lattice Boltzmann equation given by:

$$f_i^*(x, t) = f_i^{\text{eq}}(x, t) + (1 - \Omega) f_i^{\text{neq}}(x, t) \quad (1.1)$$

$$f_i(x + c_i \Delta t, t + \Delta t) = f_i^*(x, t), \quad (1.2)$$

where $f_i(x, t)$ is the Particle Distribution Function (PDF) at position x and time t for a discrete particle with velocity c_i , Δt is the time step, $f_i^{\text{eq}}(x, t)$ and $f_i^{\text{neq}}(x, t)$ are the equilibrium and non-equilibrium PDFs, which depends on the local fluid properties. Furthermore, Ω is the non-linear collision operator that is entirely local while the streaming step shown in eq. (1.2) is linear and typically requires only first neighborhood memory accesses [15].

For the collision operator used in the LBM scheme, several evolutions have been proposed over the past three decades. Originally, a very simple scheme based on the Bhatnagar et al. [2] was proposed. The so called BGK collision operator. The basic idea behind this operator was to relax all PDF values with a single relaxation time towards their equilibrium [3]. Hence, it's name single relaxation time (SRT) collision operator. While this is at the same time effective and simple, it is lacking behind in numerical accuracy and stability. Thus, the natural evolution was to propose different relaxation times (MRT) for each of the PDF values [4]. This idea comes along to shifting the PDF values to the observer space (often referred to as moment space), where each moment represents a different physical phenomenon. Hence, it came as a natural idea to think that each of these phenomena should evolve with a different speed. This advancement came with improved accuracy and stability, however also with an extended set of parameters that are tedious to tune. To simplify this a down to only two parameters (TRT), Ginzburg et al. [11] later shows a variant based on only two relaxation times, which is increases the simplicity and usability of the scheme. In the same time to extend the idea of the MRT scheme, two major improvements have been proposed by the work of Geier et al. [8, 7]. Both of which follow the idea of changing the statistical observer of the PDFs and thus shifting the collision operator to a different space. The first idea was to use the central moment space (C) where the collision can be represented in the still frame [8]. The second idea was to shift these so-called central moments further to the cumulant space [10, 6]. Hence, changing the physical observer to a cumulant based. The major advantage here is that cumulants (K) are statistically independent. Thus, the relaxation of different physical phenomena with different rates is especially effective, leading to a superior scheme in terms of physical accuracy and stability [9]. However, the implementation of this scheme is tedious and cumbersome especially because the shifting operators have to be implemented in a recursive fashion to minimize numerical round off errors and FLOPs. Due to these problems, improvements of the SRT scheme in another direction have been proposed by Latt et al. [16]. Here the idea was to use the original simple SRT equations but filter out nonhydrodynamic contributions that appear during the streaming step (RR). It could be considered as a kind of correction applied to the original scheme. As this approach showed an improvement in terms of stability and accuracy, it is not enough for highly Reynolds number flows. Thus, as a further improvement a hybrid recursive regularization (HRR) was introduced based on the idea to employ a finite difference scheme on the velocity field and couple it with the LBM collision operator to better filter out nonhydrodynamic contributions [14, 5].

In the scope of the SCALABLE project, we look at the HRR collision operator because this scheme is used in the PROLB/LABS solver. The work done here was to add this scheme to *lbmpy* and thus make use the of the code generation pipeline to generate an optimized version of the collision operator in terms of FLOPs. During the project, remarkable optimizations with *lbmpy*'s facility could have been shown here [12]. A further

Figure 1.1: Comparison of various generated collision models on NVIDIA A100 in single precision

advantage of the code generation technique is not only the mathematical optimization, but also optimizations that can be enabled for specific hardware, making the resulting compute kernel performance portable. With the addition of the HRR scheme to, *lbmpy* it was possible to compare the collision operator in terms of MLUPS to the already supported schemes. This comparison is shown in fig. 1.1. As pictured here, the HRR scheme performs about 15% slower than all other collision operators. The reason for this is the additional data needed to perform the finite difference scheme on the velocity field. All other collision models are completely local and do not require additional memory accesses. Thus, also the theoretical performance limit calculated by a roofline model with the machine bandwidth (indicated by a dashed line above the bars) is lower for the HRR scheme. These results are confirmed by the literature [21].

As a next step, the generated collision operator was tested inside the PROLB/LABS framework and a performance increase of about 30% could be observed. Thus, the combination of the code generation facility with PROLB/LABS could be considered successful and ideas emerging from this task will lead to improvements in the code basis of the industrial CFD solver.

1.2 SIMD on GPU

One of the trade-offs for massive parallelization on GPUs is the limited support for independent control flow between different threads. This can sometimes result in a missed optimization opportunity. For example, in the case of waLBerla, the compute kernel doesn't need to be executed in regions with solid domains. However, the GPU threads are not aware of this and will still execute the kernel, resulting in a waste of computational resources. A simple if condition can be used to avoid this, but it will result in a branch divergence and a performance penalty.

One of the techniques to avoid this is to use a mask to control the execution of the kernel. This mask is a boolean array that is used to control the execution of the kernel. The mask is set to true for all the threads that need to execute the kernel and false for the rest. This way, the threads that don't need to execute the kernel will be idle and will not waste any computational resources. We can use the SIMD intrinsics to implement the masking technique in CUDA.

In this section, we explore the use of this technique to avoid the execution of the compute kernel in regions with solid domains. We ultimately find that the masking technique is not very effective in this case.

1.2.1 A Prototype Implementation to Test the Masking Technique

In order to first check the effectiveness of the masking technique in general, we apply the technique to a simple kernel. The kernel is based on the logistic map function as shown below. The kernel takes in two arrays of unsigned integers and depending on whether the two values are equal or not, it computes one of the two logistic maps. This is a nice example to test the masking technique because the two branches of the if condition are completely independent of each other. Furthermore, one can control the distribution of equal and unequal values in the two arrays to control the benefit of the masking technique. A larger array of contiguous equal values will result in a larger benefit from the masking technique. Testing for different distributions of equal and unequal values, we find that we get a speedup of around 1.43 ± 0.30 for the masking technique compared to the naive implementation.

```
__global__ void compare(const unsigned int* a, const unsigned int* b,
```



```

double *rd, unsigned int *c)
{
    // this thread handles the data at its thread id
    int tid = blockIdx.x;
    double x = rd[tid];
    for(std::size_t i =0; i < 1e6 ; ++i) {
        // Non-SIMD Version
        // if(a[tid] != b[tid])
        // SIMD Version
        if(__vsetne4(a[tid], b[tid])) {
            x = 4 * x * (x-1);
        } else {
            x = 3.8 * x * (x-1);
        }
    }
    rd[tid] = x;
}

```

1.2.2 SIMD Implementation for the S2A Test Case

Having tested the masking technique on a simple kernel, we now apply the technique to the compute kernel of the S2A test case. S2A as a test case has a large number of solid cells in a single continuous region. This makes it an ideal candidate to test the masking technique. However, as opposed to the simple prototype kernel, the compute kernel of the S2A test case has a lot of data and much more computation to perform per kernel. Therefore, apart from the performance boost from the SIMD intrinsics, we also need to consider the impact that bandwidth and memory access patterns have on the performance of the masking technique. We replace the if condition in the compute kernel with the SIMD intrinsic `__vsetne4` as shown below and run our S2A test case. We notice that we do not get any performance boost from the masking technique. One of the reasons this happens is that the way SIMD intrinsics are implemented in CUDA devices, they do not reduce the number of memory accesses and therefore, in a memory-bound kernel like the S2A compute kernel, the masking technique does not provide any performance boost.

```

//SIMD if condition
if (!__vsetne4(_data_flag_field_10_20[_stride_flag_field_0*ctr_0],
              (unsigned int)8))

```

FlagField without SIMD	FlagField with SIMD
707.113 MLUPS	704.314 MLUPS
(million lattice cell updates per second)	(million lattice cell updates per second)
707.113 MLUPS / process	704.314 MLUPS / process
702.689 MFLUPS	699.908 MFLUPS
(million fluid lattice cell updates per second)	(million fluid lattice cell updates per second)
702.689 MFLUPS	699.908 MFLUPS
10789.7 time steps / second	10747 time steps /second

Table 1.1: MLUPS table for FlagField with/without SIMD

2.1 Static Mesh Refinement

In this section, we describe the basic idea behind the mesh refinement algorithm implemented in WALBERLA and the improvements done in the scope of this project. Originally, mesh refinement was introduced in WALBERLA through the work of Schornbaum et al. [19, 20]. This work led to impressive results allowing WALBERLA to employ large scale refined simulations with 197 billion grid nodes on almost 458 752 CPU cores. However, the mesh refinement was implemented with certain restrictions that were tackled during the SCALABLE project. The first problem was the pure implementation in, WALBERLA meaning the code generation facility that was later developed was not part of the mesh refinement algorithm. While the original realization was surely capable of delivering extreme scale performance, it was also limited to the LBM models provided in WALBERLA and thus could not make use of the superior flexibility introduced with the code generator *lbmpy*. This flexibility also comes with the possibility to employ in-place streaming patterns for the LBM, and thus reducing the required memory almost by a factor of two. The second problem was the usage of four ghost layers around each block in WALBERLA's block-structured grid. While this is not a major problem when using rather large blocks (e.g. 32^3 or 64^3) it makes the usage of small blocks like 8^3 unfeasible due to the high memory demand. The third problem was the restriction to CPU architectures. This point goes together with the first point because the code generation facility of *lbmpy* supports performance portability, which was shown often times on uniform grids [1, 13].

The newly developed mesh refinement algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1. As common for LBM refinement algorithms, the domain is not only spatially refined but also temporal. This is done in order to keep the speed of sound constant through all grid levels, thus employing so-called acoustic scaling. As a result, a recursive timestepping scheme emerges, where each grid level is solved two times more often than the previous one. The algorithm starts by executing a combined stream-collide step on all grid levels. This follows the grid interpolation as well as the boundary handling and the same-level communication. By same-level communication, we mean the data exchange of blocks that reside on the same grid level. Afterward, this pattern is executed in recursive fashion until the coarsest grid level is reached.

In comparison to the work of Schornbaum et al. the significant changes concern the interpolation between the grid levels. First of all the executed compute kernels for this step are no longer handwritten. Thus, the high flexibility of *lbmpy* can be used to generate specialized versions of these. This means mostly they can be generated for a variety of different lattice stencils and streaming patterns. Second, for the fine to coarse communication, a bit mask is used to ensure a correct interpolation of the PDF-arrays. A detailed explanation of this procedure can be found here [12]. This optimization allows us to remove the unnecessary four ghost layers and reduce them by two. Using only two ghost layers significantly removes the memory usage when using a large amount of especially small blocks. Furthermore, in the newly developed algorithm, only one separated streaming step is executed on the inner ghost layer. Otherwise, the streaming step is entirely executed in conjunction with the collision step. This is the ideal situation. On top of that, the cut cell method is implemented in the block level. This results in removing blocks containing only boundary cells and thus making un-refinement as described in deliverable 3.1 obsolete.

Finally, the algorithm gets executed on a block-structured grid provided by WALBERLA's octree data structure. An example of such a mesh is shown in fig. 2.1. For this example, the domain is decomposed in 33 blocks on three grid levels and four processes. As it is shown, the load-balancing algorithm uses space filling curves to balance the blocks between the processes. During the load balancing phase the block structure is not yet filled with the actual simulation data but a proxy data structure is used. This makes the preprocessing especially light-weight and allows starting the simulation from a previously balanced octree that is written to a simple text file. Hence, even largest scale simulation can almost entirely skip the preprocessing phase and start immediately from a pre balanced state where only the actual data allocation is missing before the solver can start to work.

Algorithm 1: The recursive time stepping scheme as implemented in WALBERLA. The current grid level is indicated by k , and the globally finest grid level (maximum refinement depth) is given by N . Function calls all take the grid level as an argument to indicate on which blocks their respective operations are executed

```

1 Function RecursiveTimestep( $k$ ):
2   StreamCollide( $k$ )
3   if  $k < N$  then
4     | RecursiveTimestep( $k + 1$ )
5   end
6   if  $k \neq 0$  then
7     | CoarseToFineCommunication( $k$ )
8   end
9   SameLevelCommunication( $k$ )
10  BoundaryHandling( $k$ )
11  if  $k \neq N$  then
12    | prepareInterpolation( $k$ )
13    | FineToCoarseCommunication( $k$ )
14  end
15  if  $k == 0$  then
16    | return
17  end
18  GhostLayerPropagation( $k$ )
19  StreamCollide( $k$ )
20  if  $k \neq 0$  then
21    | RecursiveTimestep( $k + 1$ )
22  end
23  SameLevelCommunication( $k$ )
24  BoundaryHandling( $k$ )
25  if  $k \neq N$  then
26    | prepareInterpolation( $k$ )
27    | FineToCoarseCommunication( $k$ )
28  end
29  return

```

Lastly, the combination of *lbmpy*'s code generation facility with WALBERLA is pictured in fig. 2.2. The complete framework build-up follows a top-down approach, where the top level is defined via the Python frameworks *lbmpy* and *pystencils*. The idea is to derive discretized equations fully symbolically using a computer algebra system in the form of *SymPy*. The discretized equations are then transformed into *pystencils*'s Intermediate representation (IR) where especially the data access is modeled via *pystencils*'s `Field`-class. From there on the compute kernel can be generated in a lower level language like C. However, due to the explicit knowledge of the later data access, it is directly possible to derive update equations for the boundary conditions as well as for the MPI-communication. The MPI-communication was extended for fields on different grid levels. Thus employing interpolation schemes in this case. The generated compute kernels can either be executed directly from Python or integrated in existing HPC codes like WALBERLA. This combines both. Rapid development in a high level language, as well as massively parallel production runs using the lower level C++ framework.

The improvements done on the refinement algorithm of WALBERLA lead to significant improvements when

Figure 2.1: Domain decomposition of the WALBERLA framework. The domain simulation domain is first partitioned and balanced using a proxy data structure. Afterward, the actual simulation data is allocated.

Figure 2.2: Complete workflow of combining *lbmpy* and WALBERLA for MPI parallel execution. Furthermore, *lbmpy* can be used as a stand-alone package for prototyping.

tackling highly complex industrial scenarios where numerous refinement levels are needed in rather small domains. These improvements can be seen best when comparing deliverable 3.1 and 2.4. While in deliverable 3.1 the simulation of the LAGOON test case was almost unfeasible with WALBERLA the situation changes drastically now. Using ten refinement levels on this test case now leads to a comparable amount of simulation cells between WALBERLA and PROLB/LABS. Additionally, the overall performance of WALBERLA is higher, which is mostly due to the highly optimized compute kernels working optimal on the uniform mesh of a single block. Lastly, integrating the code generator in the refinement algorithm allowed us to firstly port this complex step to GPUs. While the performance on GPUs is still not optimal in terms of raw performance, we clearly reached highly superior performance already when comparing the refined meshes to an equivalent uniform mesh. Thus, the time to solution is already strongly reduced. For the performance results, we can refer to deliverable 2.4 here.

Part 2

Labs

Node-Level Optimizations

3.1 Evaluation Platform and Libraries

All development work and performance evaluation was carried out on Karolina supercomputer at IT4Innovation in Ostrava, Czech republic. The most important aspects of the platform are provided in Table 3.1.

	Specification
Configuration	2x AMD EPYC™ 7H12, 64-core, 2.6 GHz
Vector cap.	256-bit wide AVX2
Memory	256 GB DDR4 3200MT/s
Network	100 Gb/s IB port per node
Compiler	GCC-11.3.0
Flags	-std=c++17 -O3 -march=native -fopenmp
MPI	OpenMPI-4.1.4

Table 3.1: Overview of most important specifications of implementation and evaluation platform Karolina.

3.2 Vectorization

Majority of modern CPU architectures possesses capabilities to apply single operation over a vector of values at once via specialized instructions. This approach is called Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) and process of turning a regular code into SIMD-enabled is called vectorization. To fully utilize the CPU core, it is necessary that application is leveraging SIMD instruction as much as possible for the computation. Although, compilers can usually produce vectorized code automatically without any modification of source code, such vectorization is often limited in terms of efficiency. It is also often the case, that compiler-driven vectorization entirely fails due to various reasons. In these situations, it is necessary to provide hints and direct the compiler to achieve it. One possible approach is to use OpenMP [18]. OpenMP is standardized set of compiler directives and functions which is designed to ease multi-threaded programming, accelerator offloading and vectorization. This standard is supported by all mainstream compilers. In ProLB, the combination of code modification and OpenMP was used.

3.2.1 Vectorization of Selected Functions

The ProLB software is very mature and complex, therefore the vectorization was carried out only on selected functions. According to Table 3.2, two selected functions for vectorization takes up **79%** and **27%** of overall run-time of COVO and LAGOON case respectively.

The vectorization itself was achieved by combination of modification to the algorithm and usage of OpenMP compilers directive. The modification of algorithm consisted of splitting the main iteration loop, which ran over all the nodes with the same properties, to single outer and several inner loops. The inner loop trip count is always equal to the SIMD vector length of particular hardware and is defined during compilation. Then the outer loop iterate over the all nodes with step equal again to vector length. The correct index is computed using outer and inner iteration variable, and vector length. By placing correct compiler directive over inner loops a cross-element vectorization was achieved. In this type of vectorization, each part of the vector computes results for different node and thus there are no dependencies between vector elements. This leads to very efficient and easily portable vectorization. Downside of this approach is that in many cases code previously factorized into functions have to be manually inlined back for vectorization to succeed which is very

laborious and error prone. In addition, each vector function has to have a scalar counterpart for the remainder of the elements in case the overall number of elements is not divisible by the vector length. This leads to large amount of code duplication.

Function	Proportion of runtime in COVO	Proportion of runtime in LAGOON
CollideFdist	66%	21%
GradientStd	13%	6%
Others	21%	73%

Table 3.2: Breakdown of time spent in vectorized functions as a percentage overall solver run-time.

Algorithm 2: The illustration of differences between a original scalar function and vectorized function obtained by algorithm modification together with the use of OpenMP compiler directives.

```

1 Function ProcessScalar():
2   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $NumberOfNodes$  do
3      $a[i] \leftarrow func1()$ 
4      $b[i] \leftarrow func2(a[i])$ 
5   end
6   return
7 Function ProcessVector():
8   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $NumberOfNodes$  by  $VectorLength$  do
9     #pragma omp simd
10    for  $k \leftarrow 0$  to  $VectorLength$  do
11       $a[i + k] \leftarrow func1()$ 
12    end
13    #pragma omp simd
14    for  $k \leftarrow 0$  to  $VectorLength$  do
15       $b[i + k] \leftarrow func2(a[i + k])$ 
16    end
17  end
18  return
19
```

3.2.2 Memory Optimizations

In addition to vectorization, another major node-level optimization was carried out – memory optimization. This optimization significantly increases the efficiency of vectorization while being independent of it, thus, benefiting all the kernel functions. It consist of separation of loop iterating over all the nodes into outer and inner loop.

The basic idea can be seen in Figure 3.1 In original design, a single kernel was applied to all the nodes before application of another kernel began. Now for a portion of nodes, all kernels are applied first before a new batch of elements begins to be processed. This substantially improves the temporal locality of the data and as such improves the performance of caches. Moreover, the batch size can be tuned for specific hardware’s memory hierarchy and capacities. The complex dependencies between various kernels required sophisticated algorithm of run-time kernel grouping to honor them. Therefore, the overall effect of this optimization is dependent on particular composition of kernels and their dependencies.

3.2.3 Evaluation

Figures 3.2 and 3.3 contain strong scaling plots of two implementations on COVO and LAGOON case respectively. The original unmodified application serving as a baseline in shown in blue and vectorized code with cache optimization applied in gray. The performance benefit of this optimization is relatively constant throughout entire examined range of processes for both cases. For COVO, the maximum increase in performance is **2-fold** while average speedup is around **60%**. In LAGOON, the maximum boost is **37%** with average around **31%**. Judging from Table 3.2 for the overall run-time of kernels selected for vectorization, the performance increase is mostly caused by better cache usage in LAGOON case.

Figure 3.1: Schema depicting (a) original kernel application and (b) memory-optimized kernel application. In original, kernels were applied one after another to all nodes. In optimized version, all kernels are applied to set of nodes before next set is processed.

Figure 3.2: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for COVO case. Original application depicted in blue and vectorization with cache optimization in gray.

Figure 3.3: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for LAGOON case. Original application depicted in blue and vectorization with cache optimization in gray.

4.1 Communication-Computation overlap

As application is scaling to more and more processors, the amount of data and work per process decreases accordingly. In general, a better performance of network is observed for smaller number of relative large messages as opposed to large number of relatively small messages. Therefore scaling impacts the communication in between processes. The payload of messages tend to get smaller and smaller with raising number of processes. After certain point, the performance of network is dominated by latency rather than bandwidth. Scaling beyond this point causes rapid increase in percentage of total run-time spent in communication. One approach to hide the communication time is to overlap it with useful work. In the area of Lattice-Boltzmann Methods (LBM), this is relatively easy to achieve. This class of methods requires only the exchange of values of nodes bordering adjacent processes' nodes. This is done by so-called halo zones which surrounds the actual nodes and are periodically filled by values from neighboring processes. In ProLB, two versions of communication-computation overlap were developed using capabilities of Message Passing Interface (MPI) library [17].

4.1.1 Simple Overlap

In the case of ProLB, the original algorithm worked in synchronized fashion. Firstly, all the independent operations were computed within all the processes. Then the halo-zone data required by other processes are sent to their particular destinations. Finally, the process waits until all the required halo-zones data from neighboring processes arrives and the algorithm continues. In this case, the communication takes place strictly after the computation and as such the overall run-time is sum of computation and communication run-times.

In order to allow for overlap to occur, the algorithm was modified in a flowing way. The computation was split into computation of halo-zone data as required by other processes and computation of the rest of nodes in inner region. Then as a first step, the halo-zone data are computed and immediately sent towards their destination. Then computation of inner region can proceed. Finally to ensure that all the data are ready for next iteration, the process waits until all incoming messages are received. The difference between two approaches can be seen in Algorithm 3.

From the implementation point of view, this required duplication and correct swapping of several buffers to comply with the MPI standard and prevent the data over-writing. It also required a major modification of communication scheme, replacement of some MPI operations by their non-blocking versions, introduction of unique tags to prevent mixing of messages sent from different iterations, and insertion of some non-blocking MPI calls to allow progress of communication. Additionally, it required development of halo-region detection algorithm based on the dependencies between nodes.

4.1.2 Overlap with Aggregation

In previous optimization the overlap between computation and communication was achieved. However, the number of messages remained the same. Another possible optimization is to reduce the amount of messages and increase the payload by widening of halo-zones. Theoretically, this has a potential to improve performance in two ways. It can improve performance of network by requiring less messages of larger size and provide better opportunity to hide communication by more useful work.

In the case of this optimization, the several halo-zone data exchange required during the iteration can be replaced by a single large halo-zone exchange at the beginning. All other required data could be computed locally within the given process causing some redundant computation. The thickness of the halo-zone and amount of required redundant computations is derived from number of halo-zones data exchange in original approach. This is illustrated in Figure 4.1, here nodes which update is required before exchange of halo-zones are shown in red, nodes required as inputs for halo-zone updates are shown in pink, and internal and external

Algorithm 3: The simplified representation of original communication schema and new schema allowing for communication-computation overlap.

```

1 Function SolverSynchronized():
2   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to NumberOfIteration do
3     for IndependentOperations in AllIndependentOperations do
4       listenForData()
5       execute(IndependentOperations)
6       sendData()
7       waitForData()
8     end
9   end
10  return
11 Function ProcessOverlaped():
12  for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to NumberOfIteration do
13    for IndependentOperations in AllIndependentOperations do
14      listenForData()
15      executeBoards(IndependentOperations)
16      sendData()
17      executeInterior(IndependentOperations)
18      waitForData()
19    end
20  end
21  return
22

```

nodes are shown in yellow and beige respectively. It can be seen that, simple overlap requires only halo-zone of thickness 1 (indicated by number of pink nodes on remote process) and requires two exchanges per iteration. The overlap with aggregation requires halo thickness of 2 while only single exchange per iteration is required. The redundant computation is depicted in this case by red nodes on remote process. These values are compute on both process N as a dependency for halo-zone updates, and process $N + 1$ during regular halo-zone computation.

Due to several limitations and complexity of this optimization, it was implemented only partially for COVO case only.

4.1.3 Evaluation

Figure 4.2 presents scaling of two optimizations of communication scheme compared to the original code. These results were achieved on COVO case. When compared to the original, the simple overlap and overlap with aggregation optimization achieved maximum improvement of **80%** and **70%** respectively and the average performance boost was **46%** and **40%** respectively. Surprisingly, both optimizations performs significantly worse than vectorization. This is most probably caused by load balancing issues with respect to the halo-zone nodes which influences the new communication schemes only. The simple overlap implementation performs better than overlap with aggregation in this case. The latter of two was implemented only as a proof of concept and suffers from several issues as excessive redundant computation. Generalization of the scheme and solving these issues would required significant effort and could be potential future work. Despite unsatisfactory result, we believe that upon finishing it has potential to improve more complex simulations.

Figure 4.3 is exactly the same as previous one but for the LAGOON case. Here in more realistic settings, the overlap optimization brings some gains compared to what was already achieved by vectorization. At best, it improves the vectorization performance by **9%** and around **5%** on average. However, the performance on 2048 processes is actually slightly worse than vectorized code. The performance benefit of overlap communication scheme is at this point negated by other performance issues as poor load-balancing. The further investigation is needed.

4.2 Multi-threading support

Majority of operating systems nowadays support the concept of thread. To simplify, threads can be thought of as lightweight processes. A single process of operating system can consist of many threads internally. These threads besides other things, can communicate with others directly via memory allocated within the encapsulating process without the need of any special mechanism. Multi-threaded processes can be leveraged to use hardware resources more effectively. A relatively small number of processes can be assigned to a single CPU each with appropriate number of threads so that overall all CPU cores are used. Because communication

Figure 4.1: Schema of halo-zone computation in both (a) simple overlap and (b) overlap with aggregation optimization.

Figure 4.2: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for COVO case. Original application depicted in blue, vectorization with cache optimization in gray, simple overlap communication scheme in green and overlap with aggregation scheme in orange.

Figure 4.3: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for LAGOON case. Original application depicted in blue, vectorization with cache optimization in gray and simple overlap communication scheme in green.

take place on process level only, multi-threading helps to minimize the overall number of messages, and as such increases the payload. However, multi-threading introduces a set of issues that needs to be accounted for as NUMA effects, first-touch policy, false shearing and race-conditions to name the few.

The OpenMP, as stated previously, support portable multi-threaded programming through various means and was chosen to implement multi-threading. In ProLB, there were two main difficulties to overcome with respect to multi-threading.

Firstly, because the ProLB application is written in Object-Oriented (OO) programming language, the data are kept and accessed in classes at different levels of inheritance hierarchy. This is not an issue for single-thread processing. However in multi-threaded execution, storing and reading by different threads causes race conditions and incorrect behavior. This was resolved by per-thread privatization of respective data members. This required relatively large modification of many classes, which proved to be very error-prone and tedious.

Secondly, the distribution of work among the threads was not straightforward. In ProLB, the nodes are firstly separated into groups based on their common features and required operations, and then these groups are split into batches which are contiguous in memory. There is a maximum size of these batches which can be fine-tuned for particular hardware. This batch of given size was originally implemented for improving the cache performance, but it also serves as a unit of work distributed among the threads. Because there are complex dependencies between different groups of elements, unusually it is not possible to process batches of different groups in parallel. Therefore, the number and size of batches of particular group assigned to the process significantly effect the effectiveness of multi-threading. Original domain decomposition algorithm was developed to only balance the load among the processes, however, it doesn't take into account the aspects of multi-threading. Therefore, the multi-threading performs well only for relatively simple cases composed mostly of single group of nodes.

Another issue affecting efficiency is presence of several critical sections within the multi-threaded regions which effectively serializes the processing. This is due to single-thread design of algorithm for message composition and output generation. These issues can be solved but would require relative large effort.

Because of issues with load balance within the process caused by presence of potentially many node groups of various sizes, the correct memory placement of the data for multi-threaded processing was not possible to achieve. As a result the NUMA affects influences performance to great degree. Therefore, ideal configuration is such that there are as many processes as NUMA regions with number of threads equal to the number of cores within the given NUMA region.

Figure 4.4: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for COVO case. Original application depicted in blue, vectorization with cache optimization in gray and multi-threading optimization consisting of 8 thread per MPI process in red.

4.2.1 Evaluation

Here, we present performance of multi-threading optimization in ProLB in Figures 4.4 and 4.5. As mentioned earlier, achieving effective multi-threaded processing of work load is relatively complicated due to architecture of ProLB. In the plots, it can be seen that efficiency decreases as application scales to more processes and work per process decreases. In COVO case, work load inside the process can be balanced better compared to LAGOON. Therefore in COVO, multi-threading achieved maximal improvement of **25%** compared to vectorized version. The average performance difference for the examined range of processes is, however, **-15%**, so overall worsening of performance. In the case of LAGOON, the performance is even worse then the performance of original code. Again, these inefficiency are caused by inability to distribute the workload inside process evenly as simulation consist of various node categories with varying node counts which don't map easily to threads. In order to make multi-threading perform better, a significant changes of application design have to be made.

4.3 Collective Communication and Load Balancing

Collectives is a communication pattern in which all the processes take place. These patterns, although optimized, can take up significant amount of time to execute when number of participating processes is high. Therefore, optimization of collective communication can substantially improve the scaling.

In ProLB's solver step, collective communication is initiated at the end of the macro iteration to gather statistics (as can be seen in Algorithm 4). The macro iteration consists of 2^n time steps where n represents the number of mesh refinement levels. During macro iteration, the nodes of the coarsest level get updated once, nodes of next finer level twice, and nodes of the finest level 2^n time. The collective communication can take significant portion of overall run-time in cases where the simulation domain is relatively homogeneous with only few levels of refinement, and/or when the amount of work per process in macro iteration is relatively small.

The simple mechanism was implemented allowing to specify the frequency of collective communication inside solver via a command line parameter in terms of number of macro iterations. This way the frequency of gathering statistics can be tuned to particular case and number of processes.

When load is not evenly distributed among the processes, chronically overloaded processes causes others to spent time waiting for the data decreasing overall efficiency even in case of loosely synchronized communication scheme. The proper Load-Balance (LB), although hard to achieve for complex cases, is crucial for improving scaling of parallel application.

For COVO case, there was an LB issue detected. For this homogeneous case, there is relatively easy way to achieve load balance by simply cutting the domain evenly into rectangular shapes based on the number

Figure 4.5: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for LAGOON case. Original application depicted in blue, vectorization with cache optimization in gray, and multi-threading optimization consisting of 8 thread per MPI process in red..

of processes. A minor design flaw of partitioning algorithm caused domain to be split into uneven shapes of various circumferences. Although overall amount of work was even among the processes, the number of halo-zone nodes differed significantly. This caused problems under new communication scheme. Therefore, a workaround was implemented to achieve distribution into even partitions to demonstrate the effect of proper load-balance. This was achievable for COVO case only. The partitioning algorithm require substantial modification to balance not only overall work but also the amount of halo-zone nodes.

Algorithm 4: Overall structure of communication during simulation including collective communication at the end of every macro iteration.

```

1 Function Solver():
2   for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to  $NumberOfMacroIterations$  do
3     for  $k \leftarrow 0$  to  $2^{NumberOfRefinements}$  do
4       for  $IndependentOperations$  in  $AllIndependentOperations[k]$  do
5         listenForData()
6         execute(IndependentOperations)
7         sendData()
8         waitForData()
9       end
10    end
11    globalGathering()
12  end
13  return
14
```

4.3.1 Evaluation

Here we present set of relatively small optimizations which elevates some of the problems encountered during assessment of previous optimization. In Figure 4.6, it can be seen that only upon resolving of all underlying issues (excessive collectives and uneven load) the overlap communication scheme was able to outperform vectorization. The maximum recorded performance increase was **31%** compared to the vectorization and **2.65-fold** compared to the original. On average, performance was increased by **19%** and **92%** respectively. The trend suggest that the performance benefits would be even more significant as the application scales to more and more processes.

In more realistic setting of LAGOON case, we were only able to implement the reduction of collective

Figure 4.6: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for COVO case. Original application depicted in blue, vectorization with cache optimization in gray, simple overlap communication scheme in green, optimization of collectives in purple and optimized collectives with balanced load in pink.

operations during simulation. Result are presented in Figure 4.7. With this optimization the maximal gain in performance was recorded at around **9%** with respect to vectorization and **46%** with respect to the original. The average gain was **5%** and **38%** respectively. Given the results for COVO, we believe that there is a opportunity to improve the performance substantially by implementing some of the proof-of-concept optimization that currently works only for that particular case. Further work is required.

Figure 4.7: Strong scaling plot comparing performance of optimizations on a range of numbers of processor for LAGOON case. Original application depicted in blue, vectorization with cache optimization in gray, simple overlap communication scheme in green and optimization of collectives in purple.

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